

Transition Metal Complexes with 3-Amino-2-methylquinazoline-4(3H)-2',4'-dinitrophenylhydrazone

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Complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with 3-amino-2-methylquinazoline-4(3H)-2',4'-dinitrophenylhydrazone have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, TG, conductance, magnetic, infrared, electronic, ^1H nmr and esr spectral data. Infrared spectra of the complexes reveal bidentate coordination by the ligand through amino nitrogen and anilino nitrogen.

A number of transition and non-transition metal complexes with different types of quinazolines and their derivatives have been extensively studied¹⁻⁴. The present paper deals with complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with 3-amino-2-methylquinazoline-4(3H)-2',4'-dinitrophenylhydrazone (hereafter HAMQDNP).

Experimental

The ligand (HAMQDNP) was prepared by the procedure as reported in literature^{5,6}. The Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Ce^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing the corresponding metal sulphate (0.005 mol) solution in aqueous ethanol with ethanol-acetone (4 : 1) solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) for 4-5 h. For the Cr^{III} , Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes, the metal chloride salts were used pH 8.0-8.6 was maintained in all the cases by adding required amount of sodium bicarbonate solution. The resulting complexes were washed with ethanol and ether. The Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes were recrystallised from ethanol and the others from DMF.

Physicochemical measurements: C, N and H estimation data were obtained from Micro-analytical Laboratory, I. I. T., Kanpur. Estimations of metal and chlorine were carried out by standard methods⁷. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes at room temperature was measured on a standard Gouy balance, mercury(II)-tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II)

($\chi = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units at 293 K) being used as calibrant. The molar conductance of solutions of the metal complexes in DMF was measured using a Systronics 303 conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr and nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20-A spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (dimethyl formamide and ethanol) on a Perkin-Elmer 4000 A spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Kanpur, ^1H nmr spectra of ligand (acetone) and the complexes (DMSO) (at room temperature) on a EM-390 90 MHz spectrometer, and esr spectra (at room temperature) on a Varian E 9 spectrometer at R.S I.C., Madras. The TG analysis was carried out on a Linseis thermogravimetric analyser.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1. Low molar conductivity values of $13-23 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for the complexes of metals other than Cr^{III} indicated their non-electrolytic nature. Molar conductivity of $115 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for the Cr^{III} complex was in agreement with 1:1 ionic nature⁸. The TGA curves of the Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes showed a weight-loss at $170-200^\circ$ that corresponds to two water molecules. The loss of water at this temperature indicates that it is coordinated to the metal ions^{9,10}. The final products of decomposition of the complexes correspond, in each case, to metallic oxide.

Infrared spectra of free ligand show band at 1650 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$)¹¹. Bands at 3300 , 3160 and 1470 cm^{-1} are attributed to ν , ν , ν , δ NH_2 , respectively⁴. The band at 3090 cm^{-1} is assigned to ν NH of anilino moiety. In all the complexes negative shift in ν , ν , ν , δ NH_2 and positive shift in δ NH_2 show coordination through amino nitrogen⁴. The disappearance of anilino band (3090 cm^{-1}) and no shift in ν $\text{C}=\text{N}$ frequency in the ir spectra of the complexes indicate coordination through anilino nitrogen and not through azo-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	N	
HAMQDNP ^a	Yellow	190	—	26.88 (27.60)	—
Cr(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃ Cl ^b	Violet	255	5.96 (6.31)	22.95 (23.33)	8.85
Fe(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃	Green	300	6.80 (7.00)	23.55 (24.50)	5.18
Co(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃	Brown	355	7.00 (7.34)	23.15 (24.40)	4.84
Mn(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃	Faint pink	305	6.21 (6.88)	23.91 (24.53)	5.93
Ni(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃	Reddish	295	7.15 (7.32)	23.15 (24.40)	3.10
Cu(AMQDNP) ₃ (H ₂ O) ₃	Dark green	275	7.86 (7.60)	23.35 (24.27)	1.91
Zn(AMQDNP) ₃	Light yellow	272	8.05 (8.45)	24.83 (25.84)	Dia.
Cd(AMQDNP) ₃	Yellow	290	13.15 (13.70)	22.75 (23.89)	Dia.
Hg(AMQDNP) ₃	Reddish brown	308	21.85 (22.07)	20.98 (21.63)	Dia.

*Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) · ^a[C, 49.80 (50.70) ; H, 3.58% (3.60)]. ^b[Cl, 4.25% (4.86)].

methine nitrogen. This is further supported by deprotonation of anilino proton in alkaline medium. The coordination through nitrogen was further confirmed by appearance of ν M-N bands¹² around 500 cm⁻¹. The ir spectra of the complexes except Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} show a broad weak band near 3 500 and 475 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of water molecule and M-O bonding¹³.

¹H nmr spectra of ligand in acetone solution show peaks at τ 1.00, 1.50, 1.65, 1.75 1.9 and 2.1 which are attributed to different ring protons¹⁴. The peak at τ 8.1 is assigned to methyl protons. A doublet at τ 7.3 and a singlet at τ 6.9 are assigned to amino and anilino protons respectively¹⁵. Nmr spectra of alkaline solution of ligand show no peak at τ 6.9. Doublet peak, appeared as singlet at τ 7.5, indicating deprotonation of anilino proton in alkaline medium.

In the complexes nmr spectra show downward shift⁴ in amino proton peak ($\tau=7.3$ in free ligand and 5.2-4.9 in the complexes) and disappearance of anilino proton peak, indicating coordination through amino nitrogen and anilino nitrogen.

Electronic spectra of Cu(AMQDNP)₃(H₂O)₃ show one asymmetric peak at 12 900 cm⁻¹ in ethanol, attributable to ³E_g→³T_{2g} transition with Jahn-Teller effect. 10 Dq value is 12 900 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=10$). The μ_{eff} value is 1.91 B.M. at room temperature. These values are in accordance with the distorted octahedral geometry of the Cu^{II} complex¹⁶.

Electronic spectra of Ni(AMQDNP)₃(H₂O)₃ exhibit three peaks at 8 500 ($\epsilon=0.7$), 14 300 ($\epsilon=1.5$) and 25 000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=2.4$). These may be assigned to (ν_1) ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F), (ν_2) ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) and (ν_3) ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(P) respectively. The ν_1/ν_2 ratio is 1.768. This corresponds to Dq/B value¹⁷ of 0.84

which gives Dq=800.27 cm⁻¹ and B=953.33 cm⁻¹. The 9.12% reduction in B value compared to Ni^{II} ion indicates complexation. Magnetic moment value of 3.10 B.M. at room temperature confirms the presence of two unpaired electrons and some orbital contribution due to mixing of excited state with lowest state¹⁸. These values are in good agreement with the reported value of octahedral geometry of the Ni^{II} complexes.

Co(AMQDNP)₃(H₂O)₃ complex shows three peaks at 9 100 ($\epsilon=0.8$), 19 200 ($\epsilon=2.0$) and 25 000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=2.8$) assigned to ⁴T_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively. Dq and B values were found to be 764 cm⁻¹ and 9.55 cm⁻¹ respectively. The B value exhibits a 14.73% reduction in comparison to free Co^{II} ion. μ_{eff} value is 4.84 B.M. at room temperature. These values are consistent with the reported value of high-spin octahedral geometry¹⁹ of Co^{II} complexes with orbital contribution.

Fe(AMQDNP)₃(H₂O)₃ complex shows a weak peak at 10 600 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=1.6$) in visible region and two broad peaks with low intensity at 31 500 ($\epsilon=2.4$) and 40 400 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=2.8$) in ultraviolet region. The first transition is attributed to ⁵T_{2g}(D)→⁵E_g(D) and the other two transitions to ⁵T_{2g}(D)→⁵T_{1g}(H) and ⁵T_{2g}(D)→⁵E_g(H) respectively. These transitions are spinforbidden and are possibly due to $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ and $\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$ transitions of the ligand or due to merger of both the transitions. Dq value of 1 060 cm⁻¹ is very close to the Dq value for octahedral Fe^{II} complexes. The μ_{eff} value is 5.13 B.M. These values are in good agreement with the reported value of high-spin octahedral²⁰ Fe^{II} complexes.

Electronic spectra of Mn(AMQDNP)₃(H₂O)₃ show three peaks at 17 000 ($\epsilon=1.0$), 26 600 ($\epsilon=2.0$)

and $28\,450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=4.6$) assigned to ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$, transitions respectively. Dq , ν_3/ν_1 , B and reduction in B values were found to be 988 cm^{-1} , 1.5, 760 cm^{-1} and 20.83%, respectively. Magnetic moment value was found to be 5.93 B.M. at room temperature which corresponds to five unpaired electrons. These values are in accordance with the reported octahedral structure of Mn^{II} complexes²¹.

$[\text{Cr}(\text{AMQDNP})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}$ shows three peaks at $16\,390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=16$), $24\,100$ ($\epsilon=16.8$) and $40\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=17.8$) assigned to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition occurs at higher energy due to merger of this peak with intra-ligand absorption. Dq and B values were found to be 972.4 cm^{-1} and 845.6 cm^{-1} respectively. B value shows a 17.8% reduction compared to the free Cr^{III} ion. Magnetic moment value was found to be 3.85 B.M. at room temperature which is slightly less than spin-only value²². These values are in accordance with the reported value of octahedral Cr^{III} complex.

$\text{Zn}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$, $\text{Cd}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$ are diamagnetic. Tetrahedral geometry is the most preferred structure for four-coordinated Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes²³. On the basis of elemental analysis, conductance, ir and ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectral data, tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the $\text{Zn}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$, $\text{Cd}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{AMQDNP})_3$ complexes.

The g_{iso} value of the Cu^{II} complex is 2.114 which is lower than that expected for truly octahedral Cu^{II} complexes indicating distortion of octahedron geometry²⁴. Isotropic hyperfine coupling constant²⁴ A_{iso} and outer s -orbital spin density²⁴ $a_s \times 100$ are 94.67 G and 9.58 respectively in the present Cu^{II} complex. These are lower than that for octahedral stereochemistry²⁴. This suggests

lesser localisation of electron on the metal giving more covalent character to the present complex.

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